

Separation and Determination of Selenium(IV) and Tellurium(IV) by using Morpholine-4-carbodithioate

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The separation and determination of selenium(IV) and tellurium(IV), when present together in a mixture, has been carried out by employing morpholine-4-carbodithioate in presence of aqueous ammonia and sulphur dioxide. The complexes were weighed as $\text{Se}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{ONS}_2)_4$ and $\text{Te}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{ONS}_2)_2$, respectively, after drying and 110-115°. The interference by Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Co^{II} , Fe^{III} , In^{III} , Tl^{III} , Sn^{II} and U^{IV} has been avoided by using an ammoniacal mixture of EDTA and tartrate (1 : 1 molar ratio) as a masking agent. The metal carbodithioates were characterised by elemental and thermogravimetric analysis.

THOUGH a number of methods¹⁻⁷ are available for the quantitative estimation of Se^{IV} and Te^{IV} , yet in the present paper the use of morpholine-4-carbodithioate has been introduced as a new gravimetric reagent for the separation and determination of selenium and tellurium. Recently, morpholine-4-carbodithioate has been studied as an analytical⁸⁻¹² and as a bidentate ligand¹³ for metal ions. In continuation of our previous work⁸⁻¹², the present paper records the results of determination and separation of Se^{IV} and Te^{IV} carbodithioates in presence of aqueous ammonia and saturated solution of sulphur dioxide. Sulphur dioxide in ammoniacal medium reduces Te^{IV} to Te^{II} , whereas Se^{IV} is masked. The complexes of sulphur trioxide with selenium have already been reported¹⁴. Sulphur dioxide reduces Se^{IV} and Te^{IV} into elementary state only in strong acidic medium¹⁵. Many metal ions do not interfere during the determination of selenium and tellurium in presence of ammoniacal EDTA and tartrate.

Experimental

The potassium salt of the reagent was prepared by mixing KOH, morpholine and CS_2 of equal ratio in ether at ice-temperature. 1% (w/v) solution of the potassium salt of the carbodithioate was prepared in distilled water.

Determination of Se^{IV} : An aliquot of SeO_2 containing 6.28-15.70 mg Se^{IV} was diluted to about 100 ml with distilled water and its pH adjusted to 4.5-5.5 by adding acetate buffer. Five-fold amount of morpholine-4-carbodithioate (1% w/v) of Se^{IV} taken, was then added for complete precipitation. Excess of the carbodithioate did not affect the weight of precipitate. The yellow precipitate, which gradually separated out, was digested at 45-50° for ~15 min on a water-bath. The precipitate was

filtered through a sintered crucible, washed repeatedly with distilled water, dried at 110-115° and weighed as $\text{Se}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{ONS}_2)_4$ (Found : C, 30.13; H, 3.98; N, 7.37. Calcd. C, 30.93; H, 4.15; N, 7.32%). The conversion factor ($\text{Se}/\text{Se-complex}$) is 0.1084.

Determination of Te^{IV} : A known volume of potassium tellurite solution containing 6.34-26.63 mg Te^{IV} was diluted to 100 ml, and 30 ml mixture of aqueous ammonia 50% (E. Merck, 0.91) and saturated sulphur dioxide solution was added to it. The contents were heated to 50-60° for about 20 min on a water-bath. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.5-6.5 by adding acetate buffer. Three-fold amount of morpholine-4-carbodithioate (1% solution, w/v) of the Te^{IV} taken was then added for complete precipitation as carbodithioate. The reddish yellow precipitate gradually separated out. Excess of the carbodithioate did not affect the weight of the precipitate. The precipitate was filtered on a sintered crucible, washed with distilled water, dried at 110-120° and weighed as $\text{Te}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{ONS}_2)_2$ (Found : C, 26.89; H, 3.26; N, 5.89. Calcd. C, 26.56; H, 3.56; N, 6.19%). The conversion factor ($\text{Te}/\text{Te-complex}$) is 0.282.

The precipitation was found to be quantitative at pH 4.0-5.5 for Se^{IV} and 5.5-6.5 for Te^{II} . The complexes are soluble in chloroform, dioxan and dimethyl sulphoxide.

Thermogravimetric studies of carbodithioates: The results of TGA curves of morpholine-4-carbodithioates of Se^{IV} , Te^{IV} and Te^{II} (heating rate 5°/min) show that they start to decompose at 150, 160 and 145°, respectively. The selenium carbodithioate is decomposed to selenium disulphide in three steps at 150-275° (Found : residue 23.0. Calcd. 24.7%), while tellurium carbodithioate decomposes in single step. Both the disulphides are finally reduced to

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elementary state at 350° (Found : residue 11.20, 17.18. Calcd. 10.8, 16.4%, respectively). Tellurium(II) carbodithioate decomposes to elementary tellurium at 340° in a single-step.

Further extension of the curves shows the volatility of the elements.

Single spot at thin-layer chromatographic plate indicates the formation of single complex of selenium(IV), tellurium(IV) and tellurium(II) with the reagent (Kmcldt). For the tlc study silica gel G (E. Merck) was used. The chloroform solutions of the complexes were spotted on the dry plates. The loaded plates were developed by ascending technique until the solvent front had travelled 100 mm (dioxan, carbon tetrachloride, benzene and a mixture of acetone-benzene (1 : 4 v/v), dioxan-carbon tetrachloride (1 : 3 v/v) and HCl-n-butanol (1 : 8 v/v). The spots of the complexes were clearly visible and so no spraying agent were required.

The formation of their disulphides as intermediate product during the heating of Se^{IV} and Te^{IV} carbodithioates, confirms that the tetravalent state of the elements is resistant to change into the divalent state, which is in good agreement with the reported observation¹⁶. The different behaviour of decomposition of aforesaid complexes may be due to some structural feature, size of the ion, and stereochemical role of the lone pair.

Quantitative separation of selenium and tellurium from their mixture : When Se^{IV} and Te^{IV} ions were present in a solution, tellurium was precipitated first as Te^{II} carbodithioate in the presence of aqueous ammonia and sulphur dioxide, thereafter in the filtrate, Se^{IV} ions were demasked by employing aqua regia and then determined as Se^{IV} carbodithioate.

A mixture containing Se^{IV} (9.42 mg) and Te^{IV} (7.64 mg) was taken in a 500 ml beaker and diluted to 100 ml with distilled water. It was then treated with equimolar (40 ml) of aqueous ammonia (50%, E. Merck 0.91) and saturated sulphur dioxide solution, and heated at 50-60° on a water-bath for 0.5 h. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.5-6.5 by using acetate buffer. 1% aqueous solution of morpholine-4-carbodithioate (w/v) was then added till the precipitation of Te^{II} was completed. The reddish yellow precipitate of Te^{II} carbodithioate which appeared within a minute, was digested at 55-65° on a water-bath for 20 min and allowed to

settle for 2 h, and then the precipitate was filtered, dried and weighed as described earlier.

The filtrate containing Se^{IV} ions was concentrated to 25% of the total volume and then treated with 10 ml of aqua regia and evaporated to almost dryness. It was diluted to 100 ml and pH adjusted to 4.5-5.5 by using acetate buffer. A yellow crystalline precipitate was obtained when the aqueous solution of morpholine-4-carbodithioate reagent was added to it and selenium was estimated according to the procedure given earlier.

TABLE 1.—SEPARATION AND DETERMINATION OF TELLURIUM AND SELONIUM

Sl. no.	Weight of Te ^{IV} taken mg	Weight of Se ^{IV} taken mg	Error %	
			Te	Se
1.	6.84	6.28	-0.47	-0.81
2.	7.64	12.56	-0.89	+0.07
3.	7.64	15.70	-0.89	-0.81
4.	20.40	9.42	+0.04	-0.42
5.	26.58	9.42	-0.80	-0.42

Effect of foreign ions on determination : To study the influence of foreign ions for the gravimetric determination of Se^{IV} (18.84 mg) and Te^{IV} (20.40 mg) a definite amount of various anions or cations was added to a definite quantity of each of the two metal ion solution prior to the addition of the morpholine-4-carbodithioate solution. pH of the solutions was adjusted as described earlier and the estimations were carried out according to the procedures given previously. It was found that the following ions do not interfere, the amount (mg) given in parenthesis : Ba^{II} (98.1), Ca^{II} (90.42), Sr^{II} (100.18), Mg^{II} (86.78), Be^{II} (74.84), Al^{III} (82.52), Th^{IV} (50.0), Zr^{IV} (79.80), nitrate (100), acetate (65.24), chloride (95.10), bromide (107.08), iodide (95.94), fluoride (100.0), citrate (64.82), tartrate (55.28), oxalate (90.20), borate (80.66), and phosphate (73.48) interfere in the determinations. The estimation of Se^{IV} and Te^{IV} has been carried out satisfactorily in the presence of (amount mg in parenthesis) Ni^{II} (76.16), Zn^{II} (100.0), Cd^{II} (94.00), Co^{II} (90.00), Fe^{III} (60.00), In^{III} (60.36), Tl^I (85.0) and Ga^{III} (53.74) using a mixture of ammoniacal EDTA and tartrate as masking agent. Cu^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pd^{II} and Pb^{II} interfere in the determinations.

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